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Climate Change-Related Crop Damage: A Significant Obstacle to Onion Farming in Kalwan Tehsil of Nashik District (MH): A Geospatial Analysis

Janardan Keshav Gavit

Abstract

Onions are an important horticultural crop cultivated worldwide for their extensive culinary use and as a spice, making them a vital component in food preparation. India ranks as the second-largest producer of onions globally; however, its yield per hectare remains lower compared to many other countries. Maharashtra is a leading state in India's onion production, contributing approximately 25% of the nation's total output. To investigate the reasons behind low onion productivity, a study was conducted to identify the challenges faced by farmers. Data were gathered from 100 farmers, with 10 participants selected from each of 10 villages in Kalwan tehsil. The results highlighted that irregular rainfall posed the most significant challenge, as reported by 74 farmers. This issue was particularly impactful during the harvest period of kharif onions and the preparation of rabi onion nurseries. In 2010, the monsoon arrived a month late and was followed by continuous rainfall until November. Unseasonal rainfall ranging from 200 to 300 mm in October and November severely damaged onion crops at various growth stages. Heavy rains in November caused substantial losses, affecting 30–40% of kharif onions ready for harvest, 15–20% of late kharif onions sown in September–October, and 20–25% of rabi onion nurseries. Additionally, the prevalence of anthracnose disease, particularly in kharif crops grown on flat beds, was exacerbated by water stagnation. Leaf damage caused by *Colletotrichum* and soil-borne diseases like bulb rot further hindered bulb development. To address these challenges, widespread adoption of techniques developed by the Directorate of Onion and Garlic Research (DOGR) is crucial. Recommended practices include the use of drip or sprinkler irrigation systems and the transplantation of seedlings on raised beds using the broad bed and furrow method, which can significantly improve onion productivity and reduce crop losses.

Key Words: Climatic change; Significant obstacle; Onion farming; Crop damage

Introduction

India holds the position of the second number largest onion producer globally, trailing only China. However, its productivity lags behind several other nations. India's average onion yield stands at approximately 16 tons per hectare, which is considerably lower than that of the USA (49 tons per hectare), the Netherlands (35 tons per hectare), and China (22 tons per hectare). Maharashtra the leading state in onion cultivation, provide 25% to the country's total production. Additionally, it dominates onion exports, accounting for 90% of India's exports, valued between Rs. 800 and 900 crores annually. Major onion-producing districts in Maharashtra include Pune, Nashik, Ahilyanagar, Dhule, Solapur, Sangali, Satara Nandurbar, Dharashiv, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, and Jalgaon. In these regions, onion farming serves as a crucial source of livelihood for rural communities.

The shift towards commercial farming is becoming more pronounced due to factors such as the evolving global market, urbanization, and increased demand for modernized agricultural products. Despite its economic significance, onion cultivation in Maharashtra is challenged by erratic rainfall patterns. Irregularities in both the amount and distribution of rainfall frequently lead to crop damage and financial strain for farmers.

Objectives

❖ To analyze how the chosen study region's onion growing is affected by climate change.

Methodology

Research was performed at Kalwan tehsil of Nashik district. Ten villages were randomly chosen for data collection: Mulane (Vani), Jaydar, Narul, Bej, Otur, Nivane, Markand Pimpri, Abhona, Chankapur, and Lingame. From each village, ten farmers were selected through a randomized sampling method, resulting in a 100 responders as the overall sample size. Data were collected using a prepared questionnaire, developed with expert input to ensure relevance and accuracy. Interviews were conducted using pre-tested schedules in the farmers' respective villages. The gathered data were systematically organized, analyzed using suitable statistical methods, and interpreted in alignment with the study's objectives.

Results and Discussion

The study findings (Table 1) highlight that the most pressing issue for 76 farmers in Kalwan tehsil was crop damage due to unpredictable rainfall. Additional major challenges included labor shortages during broadcasting (reported by 74 farmers), the distribution of counterfeit seeds by suppliers (70 farmers), insufficient scientific knowledge among farmers (66 farmers), and challenges in keeping appropriate separation distances while producing seeds (58 farmers).

Table – 1. Limitations in the First Five Villages' Onion Production and Post-Harvest Management.

Sr. No.	Limitations	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage
I.	Maintaining the necessary separation distance during seed development might be challenging.	29	58%
II.	Provided of low-quality or counterfeit seeds by seed agencies	35	70%
III.	Weed infestation issues	26	52%
IV.	Labor shortages during transplanting	37	74%
V.	Inadequate supply of fertilizers	16	32%
VI.	Insecticide, pesticide, and herbicide availability problems	9	18%
VII.	Challenges in infection and disease management	17	34%
VIII.	Insufficient scientific understanding of field operations	33	66%
IX.	Crop losses brought on by erratic rainfall	38	76%
X.	Using non-scientific techniques for packaging and grading	7	14%
XI.	Lack of proper scientific depot facilities	19	38%
XII.	High transportation costs	10	20%
XIII.	Fluctuations in market prices	22	44%
XIV.	Marketable yield is decreased because of twin bulbs, bolters, and other problems.	19	38%
XV.	A rise in fierce competition in markets	12	24%

Source: Compiled by Researcher

The analysis (Table 2) shows that heavy rainfall during kharif onion harvesting and rabi nursery preparation was the most significant constraint, impacting 70% of farmers. Other major concerns included labor shortages (68%), supply of counterfeit seeds (66%), inadequate scientific knowledge (62%), and having trouble staying isolated when producing seeds (46%).

Table - 2. Limitations in the Last Five Villages' Onion Production and Post-Harvest Handling

Sr. No.	Limitations	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage
I.	Maintaining the necessary separation distance during seed development might be challenging.	23	46
II.	Provided of low-quality or counterfeit seeds by seed agencies	33	66
III.	Weed infestation issues	20	40
IV.	Labor shortages during transplanting	34	68
V.	Inadequate supply of fertilizers	11	22
VI.	Insecticide, pesticide, and herbicide availability problems	7	14
VII.	Challenges in infection and disease management	11	22
VIII.	Insufficient scientific understanding of field operations	31	62
IX.	Crop losses brought on by erratic rainfall	35	70
X.	Using non-scientific techniques for packaging and grading	5	10
XI.	Lack of proper scientific depot facilities	14	28
XII.	High transportation costs	8	16
XIII.	Fluctuations in market prices	19	38
XIV.	Marketable yield is decreased because of twin bulbs, bolters, and other problems.	13	26
XV.	A rise in fierce competition in markets	9	18

Source: Compiled by Researcher

Overall findings (Table 3) consolidate that erratic rainfall during kharif onion harvesting and rabi nursery preparation was the leading issue, affecting 73 farmers. Labor shortages during broadcasting (71 farmers), supply of counterfeit seeds (68 farmers), limited scientific knowledge (64 farmers), and difficulty in maintaining isolation during seed

production (52 farmers) were other prominent challenges. Additional obstacles included weed infestation (46 farmers), market price fluctuations (41 farmers), lack of scientific storage facilities (33 farmers), reduced marketable yield (32 farmers), pest and disease management issues (28 farmers), fertilizer shortages (27 farmers), market competition (21 farmers), high transportation costs (18 farmers), delayed fungicide availability (16 farmers), and non-scientific grading and packaging practices (12 farmers).

Table -3. Generally, management after harvest and onion output are constrained (N=100).

Sr. No.	Limitations	Percentage
I.	Maintaining the necessary separation distance during seed development might be challenging.	52
II.	Provided of low-quality or counterfeit seeds by seed agencies	68
III.	Weed infestation issues	46
IV.	Labor shortages during transplanting	71
V.	Inadequate supply of fertilizers	27
VI.	Insecticide, pesticide, and herbicide availability problems	16
VII.	Challenges in infection and disease management	28
VIII.	Insufficient scientific understanding of field operations	64
IX.	Crop losses brought on by erratic rainfall	73
X.	Using non-scientific techniques for packaging and grading	12
XI.	Lack of proper scientific depot facilities	33
XII.	High transportation costs	18
XIII.	Fluctuations in market prices	41
XIV.	Marketable yield is decreased because of twin bulbs, bolters, and other problems.	32
XV.	A rise in fierce competition in markets	21

Source: Compiled by Researcher

Between June and December, farmers engage in kharif onion cultivation, late kharif seedling planting, and rabi nursery preparation. In 2010, a delayed monsoon by one month followed by continuous rainfall until November led to abnormal precipitation levels of 200–300 mm in key onion-growing regions during October and November. This unexpected heavy rainfall caused severe damage to onion crops at various growth stages. Erratic and premature rains significantly affected kharif onions, late kharif crops, and rabi nurseries. Specifically, 30–40% of harvest-ready kharif onions were damaged, 15–20% of late kharif crops planted in September-October suffered losses, and rabi nurseries saw 20–25% damage (NHRDF, 2010). The sowing of rabi nurseries across Maharashtra was also delayed. Additionally, kharif crops grown on flat beds—common among farmers—were more vulnerable to anthracnose disease due to waterlogging. Soil-borne conditions caused bulb spoilage and hindered bulb development, while *Colletotrichum* led to leaf damage.

To address this yield gap, the DOGR recommended innovative techniques such as transplanting seedlings on raised beds (BBF) and employing drip or sprinkler irrigation. These practices have gained popularity among farmers, leading to higher onion yields. A study by Gadge et al. (2011) revealed that while traditional flat-bed cultivation produced 10–12 tons per hectare, the adoption of raised beds and micro-irrigation systems yielded 20–25 tons per hectare under similar rainfall conditions.

Adaptation Strategies for Climate Change in Onion Farming:

- Adjusting planting schedules to avoid periods of excessive rainfall can reduce crop damage.
- Utilizing broad bed furrow (BBF) systems rather than conventional flat beds helps mitigate flood-related losses during the kharif season.
- Combining BBF planting with drip irrigation addresses water scarcity and soil salinity, enhancing crop growth.
- Micro-sprinkler irrigation helps regulate microclimates during summer, mitigating heat stress on bulb development.
- Implementing integrated pest management (IPM) that factors in rainfall patterns can improve pest control and lower fungicide expenses.
- Water-saving techniques like fertigation-based irrigation have been shown to conserve 40% water, reduce labor by 30%, and cut nitrogen use by 30%, while boosting yields by 15% .
- Soil moisture preserved by mulching with organic waste or black and white polythene, suppresses weeds, and maintains optimal soil temperatures.

Conclusion

The study highlights that erratic rainfall during the gathering of kharif onions and the composition of rabi onion nurseries emerged as the most significant challenge, impacting 73% of farmers. Variations in rainfall patterns directly and indirectly influence agricultural and horticultural productivity, with unpredictable weather conditions often leading to considerable crop losses. During the kharif and late kharif seasons, excessive rainfall and persistent cloudy weather can reduce onion yields by 60–70%. Additionally, soil-borne and fungal diseases become more prevalent due to excess moisture and inadequate drainage, further aggravating crop damage. To mitigate these challenges, the development of climate-resilient onion varieties is crucial. Moreover, adopting advanced agronomic practices such as raised bed planting, micro-irrigation, fertigation, and mulching offers effective strategies for adapting to climate change. It is essential for agricultural development

agencies to conduct extensive demonstrations of these innovative techniques to promote their adoption. Implementing these measures can significantly enhance onion yields, even in unfavourable climatic conditions.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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